

A note on the convergence of the generalized AOR iterative method for linear systems

Zhong-xi Gao and Hou-biao Li

Abstract—Recently, some convergent results of the generalized AOR iterative (GAOR) method for solving linear systems with strictly diagonally dominant matrices are presented in [Darvishi, M.T., Hessari, P.: On convergence of the generalized AOR method for linear systems with diagonally dominant coefficient matrices. Appl. Math. Comput. 176, 128-133 (2006)] and [Tian, G.X., Huang, T.Z., Cui, S.Y.: Convergence of generalized AOR iterative method for linear systems with strictly diagonally dominant coefficient matrices. J. Comp. Appl. Math. 213, 240-247 (2008)]. In this paper, we give the convergence of the GAOR method for linear systems with strictly doubly diagonally dominant matrix, which improves these corresponding results.

Keywords—Diagonally dominant matrix, GAOR method; Linear system, Convergence

I. INTRODUCTION

CONSIDER, the linear system

$$Hy = f \quad (1)$$

where

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} I - B_1 & D \\ C & I - B_2 \end{bmatrix},$$

is an invertible matrix. For example, in the generalized least squares problem [3], [4], we must solve the generalized least squares problem

$$\min_{x \in R^n} (Ax - b)^T W^{-1} (Ax - b),$$

where W , is the variance-covariance matrix [5]. If $I - B_i$ for $i = 1, 2$ are nonsingular, we can apply the regular AOR method, or the regular AOR method [6] to solve (1). However, $I - B_i$ for $i = 1, 2$ sometimes are singular. In fact, even if $I - B_i$ are nonsingular, it is also not easy to solve linear system (1) because we have to find the inverses of $I - B_i$ for $i = 1, 2$, or to solve two subsystems

$$(I - B_i)x_i = d_i, i = 1, 2.$$

Hence a generalized AOR (GAOR) method was proposed by Yuan to solve linear system (1) in [3], afterwards, Yuan and Jin [4] established a generalized AOR (GAOR) method to solve linear system (1) as follows.

$$y^{k+1} = G_{\omega, \gamma} y^k + \omega k, \quad (2)$$

where

$$G_{\omega, \gamma} = (1 - \omega)I + \omega J + \omega \gamma K,$$

Authors are with the School of Mathematics Sciences, University of Electronic Science and Technology of China, Chengdu, 610054, PR China. Corresponding author, e-mail: (lihoubiao0189@163.com).

$$k = \begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ -\gamma C & I \end{bmatrix} f,$$

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} B_1 & -D \\ -C & B_2 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ C(I - B_1) & CD \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ C \end{bmatrix} [I - B_1 \quad D].$$

From the above, we know that the GAOR method does not need any inverse of $I - B_i$ for $i = 1, 2$. It is easy to check that the GAOR method is the GSOR method when $\omega = \gamma$; the generalized Jacobi method when $\gamma = 0$; and the regular AOR method [5] when $B_1 = B_2 = 0$.

Throughout this paper, we shall employ the same notations as in [1], [2]. For instance, $N \triangleq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, denote the class of all complex matrices by $C^{n, n}$, and denote $\rho(G_{\omega, \gamma})$ by the spectral radius of iterative matrix $G_{\omega, \gamma}$.

For $A = (a_{ij}) \in C^{n, n}$, let

$$R_i(A) = \sum_{j \neq i} |a_{ij}|.$$

Recall that A is said to be strictly diagonally dominant ($A \in SD$), if

$$|a_{ii}| > R_i(A), \forall i \in N,$$

and if

$$|a_{ii}| |a_{jj}| > R_i(A) R_j(A), \forall i, j \in N, i \neq j.$$

we call that A is strictly doubly diagonally dominant ($A \in SDD$). Obviously, $SD \subseteq SDD$.

In [1], [2], the following main results are presented:

Theorem 1.1 ([1]) Let $H \in SD$, then $\rho(G_{\omega, \gamma})$ satisfies the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned} |\omega - 1| + \min_i \{ |\omega| J_i + |\omega \gamma| K_i \} &\leq \rho(G_{\omega, \gamma}) \leq \\ |\omega - 1| + \max_i \{ |\omega| J_i + |\omega \gamma| K_i \}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where J_i and K_i are the i -row sums of the modulus of the entries of J and K , respectively.

Theorem 1.2 ([2]) Let $H \in SD$, then $\rho(G_{\omega, \gamma})$ satisfies the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned} \min_i \{ |\omega - 1| - |\omega| (J + \gamma K)_i \} &\leq \rho(G_{\omega, \gamma}) \leq \\ \max_i \{ |\omega - 1| + |\omega| (J + \gamma K)_i \}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $(J + \gamma K)_i$ denotes the i -row sums of the modulus of the entries of matrix $J + \gamma K$.

In this note, we will continue to study this problem and obtain some new inequalities which improves the corresponding results in [1], [2].

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, based on our results [8], [9], we obtain new upper and lower bounds for the spectral radius of $G_{\omega,\gamma}$ when $H \in SDD$, which is better than one of Theorem 1.1 and Theorem 1.2. In Section 3, we discuss the convergence of the GAOR method for SDD. In Section 4, we present numerical examples to show that our results are better than Theorem 1.1 and 1.2.

II. UPPER AND LOWER BOUNDS FOR $\rho(G_{\omega,\gamma})$

Theorem 2.1 Let $H \in SDD$. Then $\rho(G_{\omega,\gamma})$ satisfies the following inequality

$$\rho(G_{\omega,\gamma}) \geq \max \left\{ 0, \min_{i \neq j} \{ |\omega - 1| - |\omega| \sqrt{(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j} \} \right\}, \quad (5)$$

or

$$\rho(G_{\omega,\gamma}) \leq \max_{i \neq j} \left\{ |\omega - 1| + |\omega| \sqrt{(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j} \right\}. \quad (6)$$

Proof. Let λ be an arbitrary eigenvalue of iterative matrix $G_{\omega,\gamma}$, then

$$\det(\lambda I - G_{\omega,\gamma}) = 0. \quad (7)$$

We can show that Eq.(7) holds if and only if

$$\det((\lambda + \omega - 1)I - \omega J - \omega \gamma K) = 0.$$

If we take the parameter γ, ω and λ in order that

$$(\lambda + \omega - 1)I - \omega J - \omega \gamma K \in SDD,$$

i.e., for any $i, j \in N, i \neq j$,

$$\omega^2((J + \gamma K)_i - (J + \gamma K)_{ii})((J + \gamma K)_j - (J + \gamma K)_{jj}) < |\lambda + \omega - 1 - \omega(J + \gamma K)_{ii}| |\lambda + \omega - 1 - \omega(J + \gamma K)_{jj}|$$

then λ is not an eigenvalue of $G_{\omega,\gamma}$, where $(J + \gamma K)_{ii}$ denotes the diagonal element of matrix $J + \gamma K$.

Obviously, especially when

$$\omega^2(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j < |\lambda + \omega - 1|^2, \forall i, j \in N, i \neq j,$$

i.e.,

$$|\omega| \sqrt{(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j} < |\lambda + \omega - 1|$$

then λ can not an eigenvalue of $G_{\omega,\gamma}$. Hence if λ is an eigenvalue of $G_{\omega,\gamma}$, we must have

$$|\lambda + \omega - 1| \leq |\omega| \sqrt{(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j},$$

especially,

$$||\lambda| - |\omega - 1|| \leq |\omega| \sqrt{(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j},$$

or

$$|\omega - 1| - |\omega| \sqrt{(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j} \leq |\lambda| \leq |\omega - 1| + |\omega| \sqrt{(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j}.$$

i.e.,

$$\rho(G_{\omega,\gamma}) \geq \max \left\{ 0, \min_{i \neq j} \{ |\omega - 1| - |\omega| \sqrt{(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j} \} \right\},$$

or

$$\rho(G_{\omega,\gamma}) \leq \max_{i \neq j} \left\{ |\omega - 1| + |\omega| \sqrt{(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j} \right\}.$$

So the assertion holds. The proof is completed. \square

Remark 2.1 The results (5) and (6) of Theorem 2.1 are better than ones of Theorem 1.1 and Theorem 1.2, since for any $i, j \in N, i \neq j$

$$\min_i \{(J + \gamma K)_i\} \leq \sqrt{(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j} \leq \max_i \{(J + \gamma K)_i\}. \quad (8)$$

In addition, for some values of γ and ω , the GAOR method reduces to the well-known methods, i.e.,

- 1) The GAOR method reduces to the GSOR method when $\omega = \gamma$, thus

$$\rho(G_{\omega,\omega}) \geq \min_{i \neq j} \left\{ 0, |\omega - 1| - |\omega| \sqrt{(J + \omega K)_i (J + \omega K)_j} \right\},$$

$$\rho(G_{\omega,\omega}) \leq \max_{i \neq j} \left\{ |\omega - 1| + |\omega| \sqrt{(J + \omega K)_i (J + \omega K)_j} \right\}.$$

- 2) The GAOR method reduces to the generalized Jacobi method when $\gamma = 0$, thus

$$\rho(G_{\omega,0}) \geq \min_{i \neq j} \left\{ |\omega - 1| - |\omega| \sqrt{J_i J_j} \right\},$$

$$\rho(G_{\omega,0}) \leq \max_{i \neq j} \left\{ |\omega - 1| + |\omega| \sqrt{J_i J_j} \right\}.$$

III. CONVERGENCE OF THE GAOR METHOD

Theorem 3.1 Let $H \in SDD$ and assume that γ and ω satisfy

$$\max_{i \neq j} (J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j < 1$$

and

$$0 < \omega < \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{\max_{i \neq j} (J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j}}, \forall i, j \in N.$$

then the GAOR is convergent.

Proof. By Theorem 2.1, we see that $\rho(G_{\omega,\gamma}) < 1$ if

$$|\omega - 1| + |\omega| \sqrt{(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j} < 1, \forall i, j \in N, i \neq j.$$

Hence, ω must satisfy $0 < \omega < 2$.

Next, we consider the following two cases:

Case 1: If $0 < \omega \leq 1$, i.e.,

$$(J + \omega K)_i (J + \omega K)_j < 1, \forall i, j \in N.$$

Case 2: If $1 < \omega < 2$, i.e.,

$$0 < \omega < \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{(J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j}}, \forall i, j \in N, i \neq j.$$

which implies

$$(J + \omega K)_i (J + \omega K)_j < 1, \forall i, j \in N, i \neq j.$$

Combining Case 1 with 2, we get

$$\max_{i \neq j} (J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j < 1$$

and

$$0 < \omega < \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{\max_{i \neq j} (J + \gamma K)_i (J + \gamma K)_j}}, \forall i, j \in N, i \neq j.$$

Hence the assertion holds. The proof is completed. \square

According to the inequality (8), our results are obviously better than the ones in [1], [2]. In addition, some other conclusions in [1], [2] may be also obtained similarly. Here, we can not describe these results in detail.

IV. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

The following two simple examples show that the results of Theorem 2.1 are better than ones of Theorem 1.1 and 1.2.

Example 4.1 Let

$$H = \left[\begin{array}{ccc|ccc} 1 & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{6} & 1 & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{3} & 1 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{array} \right] = \begin{bmatrix} I - B_1 & D \\ C & I - B_2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Clearly, $H \in SD$. Meanwhile, $H \in SDD$. For convenient, supposing that $\omega = \gamma = 1.0$. By Theorem 2.1, we have $0 \leq \rho(l_{\omega, \gamma}) \leq 0.5046$, but we have, by Theorem 1.2, $0 \leq \rho(l_{\omega, \gamma}) \leq 0.8333$. In fact, $\rho(l_{\omega, \gamma}) = 0.2392$. These show that our results are better than ones of Theorem 1.1 and 1.2.

Example 4.2 Let

$$H = \left[\begin{array}{ccc|ccc} 1 & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{6} & 1 & \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{3} & 1 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{array} \right] = \begin{bmatrix} I - B_1 & D \\ C & I - B_2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Obviously, $H \in SDD$, but $H \notin SD$, therefore Theorem 1.1 and Theorem 1.2 are not valid. For convenient, supposing that $\omega = \gamma = 1.0$. By Theorem 2.1, we have

$$0 \leq \rho(l_{\omega, \gamma}) \leq \frac{\sqrt{35}}{6} < 1,$$

which shows that our conclusions are valid.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Darvishi, M.T., Hessari, P.: On convergence of the generalized AOR method for linear systems with diagonally dominant coefficient matrices. Appl. Math. Comput. 176(2006), 128-133.
- [2] Tian, G.X., Huang, T.Z., Cui, S.Y.: Convergence of generalized AOR iterative method for linear systems with strictly diagonally dominant coefficient matrices. J. Comp. Appl. Math. 213(2008), 240-247.
- [3] Yuan, J.Y.: Numerical methods for generalized least squares problems. J. Comp. Appl. Math. 66, 571-584 (1996).
- [4] Yuan, J.Y., Jin, X.Q.: Convergence of the generalized AOR method. Appl. Math. Comput. 99(1999), 35-46.
- [5] Searle, S., Casella, G., McCulloch, C.: Variance Components. Wiley Interscience, New York, 1992.
- [6] Hadjidimos, A.: Accelerated overrelaxation method. Math. Comput. 32(141)(1978), 149-157.
- [7] Hadjidimos, A., Yeyios, A.: The principle of extrapolation in connection with the accelerated overrelaxation method. Linear Algebra Appl. 30(1980), 115-128.

- [8] Li, Hou-Biao, Huang, T. Z. and Li H., An improvement on a new upper bound for moduli of eigenvalues of iterative matrices, Appl. Math. Comp. 173(2006), 977-984.
- [9] Huang, T. Z., Gao Zh. X., A new upper bound for moduli of eigenvalues of iterative matrices, Intern. J. Computer Math., 80(6)(2003), 799-803.

Zhong-xi Gao is with the School of Mathematics Sciences, University of Electronic Science and Technology of China (UESTC), China. His current research interests include linear algebra and its application, matrix theory, especially combinatorics and graph theory.
Email: zhongxigao@126.com

Hou-biao Li received the M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees in computational and applied mathematics from University of Electronic Science and Technology of China (UESTC), China, in 2005 and 2007, respectively. He currently is an Associate Professor with the School of Mathematics Sciences, UESTC. His research interests involve numerical linear algebra, preconditioning technology and computational mathematics, etc.
Email: lihoubiao0189@163.com